

THE ROLE OF THE PRESIDENT IN THE LEGISLATIVE PROCESS**E. Gazvinova**

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Abstract

One of the important features that characterize the status of the President as head of state is the signing of laws adopted by the Milli Majlis. The President's refusal to sign a law is called a veto. The constitution does not use the word "veto". This is one of the elements of the system of "checks and balances", which are the essence of the principle of separation of powers. The veto creates a real opportunity to return the law for the purpose of amendments and reconsideration of the issue of compliance with the goals of its adoption.

The time allotted for the signing of the law is sufficient. This is explained by the fact that the laws submitted for signing to the President may be of different volumes, and familiarization with them may take time. As head of the executive branch, the President is responsible for the outcome of the application of the law. For this reason, predicting the results of applying the law.

Keywords: President, decree, order, act, law-making

The concept of the distribution of powers plays an important role as the basis of the structure of state power and determines the principles of the organization of state power in most countries. However, thinkers of ancient and modern times (Aristotle, K. Locke, etc.) argued that the activity of the state is not homogeneous and includes several types of activity - legislative activity, executive activity and justice. It was noted here that various state bodies specialize in the execution of a particular activity. Based on these ideas, the eighteenth-century French philosopher and historian C. L. Montesquieu created the theory of "separation of powers", which was accepted as a classical theory. In his opinion, there can be no single authority with a duly established state, but rather three powerful powers - legislative, executive and judicial. Any combination of these types of power in the hands of a body or a person will necessarily lead to forgetfulness of the interests of the people, misuse and does not fit into the political freedom of the individual.

The most important powers of the President in relations with the highest representative body are the possibility and degree of participation of the President in the legislative process. In some countries (the United States and other states), the president is not required to participate in official parliamentary activities. There are countries in which (eg, India, etc.), along with the chambers, the president is also part of the parliament.

In presidential republics, the powers of the head of state are more restrictive. However, the activity of the head of state significantly reduces their official speed. For example, the use of the right of the head of state to the right of veto, adopted by parliament, serves these purposes.

It is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the President actively participates in the legislative process. The Milli Mejlis does not take any part in the adoption of decrees. The president independently adopts decrees, does not need the institution of a countersignature. Exceptions are decrees adopted to establish a state of emergency and martial law (Articles 111 and 112 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan). This, first of all, allows public administration in

various spheres of public life - the right of the executive branch, which implements the functions of the executive branch, to more carefully control existing relations with the public and to carry out a more legislative initiative of the president as the head of the executive branch.

Among a number of extensive powers of the President, the law-making functions of the President are important. The President of the Azerbaijan Republic may act with the right of legislative initiative. This is his constitutional mandate.

The following powers of the President in the legislative process can be distinguished:

- The right to act as a subject of legislative initiative.
- Signs the law
- Promulgation of laws on amendments to the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, constitutional laws and current laws.
- Publish the law
- Has the right to veto
- May apply to the Constitutional Court with a request in connection with the issues provided for by parts III and IV of Article 130 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan

The first right has not only the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, but also other entities specified in Art. 96 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The remaining rights relate exclusively to the powers of the head of state. It is no secret that the laws adopted by the Milli Majlis on the basis of the legislative initiative of the President have the greatest weight. This, first of all, allows public administration in various spheres of public life - the right of the executive branch, which implements the functions of the executive branch, to be more closely monitored by existing public relations and to carry out a more legislative initiative of the president as head of the executive branch. Practice shows that the Milli Majlis and the President most often use the right of legislative initiative.

Draft laws introduced by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan may not gain the appropriate vote.

One of the important features that characterize the status of the President as head of state is the signing of laws adopted by the Milli Majlis. The President's refusal to sign a law is called a veto. The constitution does not use the word "veto". This is one of the elements of the system of "checks and balances", which are the essence of the principle of separation of powers. The veto creates a real opportunity to return the law for the purpose of amendments and reconsideration of the issue of compliance with the goals of its adoption.

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of state categorically rejects a bill approved by parliament. Usually the veto is imposed on the entire law. But in some countries (Argentina, Mexico), the president has the right to veto certain articles and provisions of the bill, which, in his opinion, will change the bill.

As a general rule, the complicated method should be set aside to remove the veto. For example, in the United States, the president's veto power, especially the veto he actively uses, can only be removed if the bill is won by a majority (two-thirds) of the majority in both houses of Congress.

The veto, called the "clash of the veto" used by the president in American life, is actually a kind of veto. The crux of the matter is that if the president decides to sign a bill approved by Congress ten days before the end of the session, the bill will not go into effect but will not be returned to Congress strictly.

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